
Subject Section

Federated OmicsDI: Cloud-based architecture for omics data discovery

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Abstract

Motivation: Omics Discovery Index (OmicsDI - www.omicsdi.org) is an integrated and open-source platform to facilitate the discovery and dissemination of omics datasets metadata. It provides a unique infrastructure to integrate datasets coming from multiple omics studies, including at present proteomics, genomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics, and systems biology. The OmicsDI architecture was originally implemented and deployed in a dedicated high-performance computing cluster, limiting scalability and dynamic allocation of resources by the data processing pipelines. In addition, the original OmicsDI resource could not be reused by independent laboratories and research groups to share and disseminate their data.

Results: Here, we present a new version of OmicsDI that can be easily deployed in cloud architectures and local infrastructures enabling the development of a Federated OmicsDI. The new architecture can be automatically synchronized with the main OmicsDI resource, increasing the integration with other omics data providers. Also, the proposed Cloud-based architecture is more scalable, providing better capabilities to manage the increase of data providers and datasets.

Availability and implementation: The software is freely available at <https://github.com/OmicsDI>

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Supplementary information: Supplementary data are available at *Bioinformatics* online.

1 Introduction

OmicsDI (www.omicsdi.org) (Perez-Riverol, et al., 2017; Perez-Riverol, et al., 2019) is a key open-source platform to integrate datasets metadata from many different omics databases into a single framework and interface. It makes life-science data more findable, accessible, and interoperable for both researchers and machines. OmicsDI used an efficient indexing system, which can integrate the metadata of each dataset and also the relevant biological entities associated with it like identified proteins, or genes changing their expression. A set of pipelines update the resource every

time a new dataset becomes publicly available in the contributing repository. By January 2021, OmicsDI provides metadata for over 2.3 million datasets, and the number will keep growing every month. In addition to indexing datasets from major omics archives such as the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), OmicsDI was designed to integrate datasets from smaller independent research laboratories. By supporting independent research groups and laboratories, OmicsDI aims to cover data providers that can't make their data public in major archives due to multiple reasons including volume or clinical and human protected datasets. However, the original implementation of the framework was linked to a specific high-performance computing architecture (HPC); limiting the possibility to reuse the OmicsDI framework by independent laboratories and consortiums

that do not have the same HPC architecture. Also, with the increase of datasets and data providers, the scalability of the processing and data injection pipelines was affected.

Cloud architectures such as Google Cloud, Amazon, or other private cloud architectures (e.g., OpenShift) have matured rapidly, creating new data centers, lowering prices, and adding new bioinformatics services. In the cloud-computing model, computational resources like processors and hard disks can be requested on demand when the application needs them. Users request resources, use them, then release them back into the pool when the work is complete. This model provides more scalability, availability, and easy deployment environments for bioinformatics resources and workflows. While cloud architectures have been extensively explored for bioinformatics workflows and tools, resources and databases are mainly deployed in dedicated architectures.

Here, we present the Federated OmicsDI, a cloud-based version of OmicsDI that can be easily deployed in cloud architectures and local infrastructures. It provides better capabilities to manage growing data and the increased demand for computational resources by the data processing pipelines. The Federated OmicsDI uses the Kubernetes framework as a container orchestration system and Spring DataFlow.

Design and Implementation

We have used Spring Cloud Dataflow (<https://spring.io/projects/spring-cloud-dataflow>), Kubernetes (<https://kubernetes.io/>), Docker (<https://www.docker.com/>), MongoDB (<https://www.mongodb.com/>), and Amazon S3 to make OmicsDI cloud deployable. Figure 1 shows the new architecture, including the OmicsDI pipelines, MongoDB database, RESTful API, and Web application frontend component. Each OmicsDI job/task is scheduled in Spring Cloud DataFlow (e.g., import data from a provider, compute statistics). Spring Cloud Dataflow is used for batch processing of data pipelines, offloading jobs to Kubernetes to orchestrate docker images generated from each pipeline (<https://github.com/OmicsDI>). Docker containers encapsulate each pipeline task; tasks are executed sequentially to create a pipeline where the output of intermediate tasks becomes the input of subsequent tasks. Continuous integration automatically deploys the REST API (e.g., <http://dev.omicsdi.org/ws/>) and Web frontend (e.g., <http://dev.omicsdi.org>) using Kubernetes.

Figure 1: Federated OmicsDI cloud-model architecture.

All pipelines are scheduled daily to retrieve data from OmicsDI providers such as ArrayExpress and GEO. The ingestion pipelines synchronize data from each provider into an S3 bucket, from where they are consumed by the processing pipelines. Deployment of the MongoDB cluster as Kubernetes *StatefulSets* makes it more resilient and available, guaranteeing no data loss even when instances crash.

The OmicsDI cloud architecture can be deployed and executed on any cloud provider that supports Kubernetes. There are two groups of environments, including web services and dataflow groups. We separated those groups because of the different usage patterns, one for retrieving data and the other for collecting data, sharing the same MongoDB stateful set instance. Dataflow services normally will create a group of pods on daily basis, for fetching as well as enriching the datasets. By separating those environments, the setup avoids conflicts between the web services (RESTful API and Web application) (**Supplementary Information Note 1**) and the pipeline environments (**Supplementary Information Note 2**). The deployment uses Kubernetes Secrets to protect sensitive information, such as MongoDB credentials, client keys, or client authentication to 3rd party services that the setup connects to. In addition, we provide a simple mechanism to deploy the infrastructure using helm charts (**Supplementary Note 3**).

2 Future Directions

The present implementation and cloud-based design provide a scalable, easy to deploy, cost-effective, and fault-tolerance OmicsDI framework. We have made our application scalable to cater to the needs of the exponential growth of data as we can increase or reduce hardware allocation (storage, RAM, CPU) at any time without downtime. The current architecture is not restricted to any cloud provider as we are using Docker and Kubernetes for container deployment, which can be easily spun up on any cloud provider. We believe the presented Cloud infrastructure will enable us to scale OmicsDI to process more providers and accept more datasets without impact on user experience. In addition, the new implementation can be deployed in local private cloud architectures and small research laboratories can use it to serve their private data.

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